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THE ECOLOGY OF CORPORATE GOVERNANCE: THE OWNERSHIP STRUCTURE FOCUS

The paper develops an ecological perspective on corporate governance by conceptualising ownership structure as a dynamic system of interacting actors rather than a set of isolated governance mechanisms. Departing from traditional approaches that analyse ownership, boards, capital structure or management separately, the study argues that corporate governance exhibits ecological characteristics, including simultaneous interaction among its components, interdependence, and a tendency towards dynamic equilibrium. Changes in one governance mechanism are assumed to propagate through the system, indirectly influencing other mechanisms and ultimately firm performance.

The paper focuses specifically on ownership structure and advances the view that owners should be understood as heterogeneous actors characterised by distinct preferences, governance strategies, and governance capacities. These attributes shape both passive and active interactions among owners, which may overlap, complement, or compete. Such interactions influence not only corporate decision-making and performance outcomes but also the evolution of the ownership structure itself through processes of entry and exit. The study highlights that similar performance outcomes may arise from different configurations of owners and interactions, emphasising the importance of equifinality in understanding corporate governance outcomes.

The paper further discusses the implications of the ecological perspective for governance theory and empirical research. It challenges the dominance of *ceteris paribus* assumptions and single-theory explanations, arguing instead for multi-theoretical and system-oriented approaches capable of capturing interaction effects. Methodological implications are addressed, including the limitations of cross-sectional designs and the need for longitudinal and configurational methods, such as fuzzy set qualitative comparative analysis, to analyse complex ownership dynamics. The paper concludes that while the ecological view increases realism and relevance, it also poses significant challenges to parsimony and empirical testing, thereby opening new directions for future research in corporate governance.

Key words: corporate governance; ownership structure; ecological perspective; owner interaction; governance mechanisms; firm performance; dynamic systems; equifinality.

Коллін Свен-Олоф. Екологія корпоративного управління: аспекти структури власності.

У статті розроблено екологічний підхід до аналізу корпоративного управління, у межах якого структура власності розглядається не як ізольований механізм впливу, а як динамічна система взаємодіючих суб'єктів із властивими їй екологічними характеристиками, зокрема множинністю та одночасністю взаємодій, взаємозалежністю елементів і тенденцією до динамічної рівноваги. Обґрунтовується теза, що корпоративне управління функціонує як складна система, у якій зміни одного механізму можуть опосередковано впливати на інші елементи управління та результати діяльності підприємства.

Основну увагу зосереджено на структурі власності як ключовому елементі корпоративного управління. Власники інтерпретуються як гетерогенні актори, що відрізняються за своїми уподобаннями, управлінськими стратегіями та управлінськими можливостями. Показано, що саме ці атрибути визначають характер як пасивних, так і активних взаємодій між власниками, які можуть мати характер накладання, взаємодоповнення або конкуренції. Такі взаємодії впливають не лише на стратегічні рішення корпорації та її результативність, а й на еволюцію самої структури власності через процеси входу та виходу власників.

У статті підкреслюється значення концепції еквіфінальності, відповідно до якої однакові результати діяльності підприємства можуть досягатися за різних конфігурацій власників і моделей їхньої взаємодії. Це дозволяє відійти від спрощених лінійних пояснень і зосередитися на аналізі системних ефектів та взаємодії факторів. Обґрунтовано обмеженість традиційних підходів, що базуються на припущенні *ceteris paribus* та переважному використанні агентської й інституціональної теорій, і доведено доцільність застосування багатотеоретичних і конфігураційних підходів.

Окрему увагу приділено методологічним наслідкам екологічного підходу. Показано, що аналіз складних взаємодій у структурі власності потребує використання поздовжніх досліджень та методів, здатних враховувати множинність причинно-наслідкових зв'язків, зокрема методів якісного порівняльного аналізу нечітких множин (fsQCA). Зроблено висновок, що, попри зростання складності теоретичного й емпіричного аналізу, екологічний підхід дозволяє суттєво підвищити аналітичну глибину та прикладну релевантність досліджень у сфері корпоративного управління, окреслюючи перспективні напрями подальших наукових пошуків.

Ключові слова: корпоративне управління; структура власності; екологічна

перспектива; взаємодія власників; механізми управління; ефективність фірми; динамічні системи; еквіфінальність.

Ontology and critique leading to an ecological view

An ontological claim suggests that corporate governance is a system of actors, structures and processes that through the corporation influence the direction of the firm and thereby influence the performance of the firm. Since it is a system, it has the ecological trait of multiple and simultaneous impact, where a single change in the system or an external impact propagates in the system, influencing several parts of the corporate governance system. It may be assumed – though empirical confirmation is pending –, that the ecological system of corporate governance has the ecological traits of balance, i.e., the system strives for equilibrium.

A more established and common ontological view is that corporate governance is a set of mechanisms that directs the corporation [16] and thereby influences the firm. The mechanisms are structures, less often processes, consisting of actors, directed by self-interest (agency theory) or guided by institutions (institutional theory). Among the structures are the ownership structure, the annual meeting of the shareholders, the charter of the corporation, the corporate law, the board, the organizational structure and its strategy, the capital structure of the corporation, the top management team, the accounting system, the share market with its actors and its regulations, the auditor, the mass media, the product markets and so on.

There is a tendency to treat these parts separately or to focus on a few of them. This is partly driven by the scientific methodological belief in the possibility to do so, i.e., to use *ceteris paribus* as a spell against multiplicity and unknown interactions, i.e., complexity [6]. Researchers tend to select one or a few of the mechanisms and theorize how these mechanisms influence the corporation, and especially its performance. Dominant theories predicting relationship between the mechanism and the direction of the corporation are the economic theory of agency theory and the sociological oriented institutional theory, with very few studies, especially in recent times, using Marxism, which is surprising given the fact that Marxism has a power focus, which is the essence of corporate governance, and have a dialectical view, which is close to the ecological perspective.

The most straightforward criticism that can be directed towards this research orientation is that it does not consider that corporate governance is a system, and therefore excludes characteristics of a system, such as an ecological dynamic process where the mechanisms are related to each other and influence each other.

It is, for example, assumed that the rights of the owners are delegated to the board that can use them or delegate them further, in a linear fashion. It can, however, be claimed that rights can be distributed in a constellation [9], giving the governance a character not of linearity but of a complex system. It has also been found that board functions, that normally is assumed to be located at the board, are scattered in the corporation and among owners [1], thus creating a constellation of functions that is not located at the presumed single organizational entity, the board. Ponomareva, Federo, Aguilera and Collin [15] found similar constellations of board practices related to firm performance. Finally, Collin, Smith, Umans, Broberg and Tagesson [10] found surprisingly that internationalisation of corporate governance had no significant influence on firm performance, partly explained by the fact that the study did not consider that the mechanisms could interact in a governance strategy, which is a concept that will be considered in later in the text.

Imagine that there is a change in one mechanism: the capital structure. An increase in debt-to-equity raises financial risk, which could induce a change in another mechanism, for example the ownership structure, where owners with preferences for low financial risk will exit the ownership structure and thereby change its composition, which in turn could influence a change in another mechanism, the set-up of directors at the board, which in turn could influence the strategy of the firm and could lead to, for example, an increase in profitability. A normal CG study, ignoring corporate governance as a system and therefore do not consider ecological processes, would correlate capital structure with profitability and conclude that leverage increases profitability. While true in a limited sense, it is not necessarily true that it is the very change in the capital structure that influence the profitability. It could be, as in the example, an indirect cause through the chains of changes just described, where maybe the change of the board is

the main cause. It could also be the case that it is the chain of changes that together and jointly influence the performance.

The second criticism, which also steams from the ecological character of the system of corporate governance, is that studies selecting one or a few mechanisms make random choices and disregard randomly others. Since we do not consider all the mechanisms and the interaction effects, ultimately the system effect, we cannot find empirically which mechanisms or which interaction effects, or the joint interaction effects that are responsible for most performance effects, i.e., we cannot find their performance weight in the governance system. Since we lack an ecological theory predicting relative performance effects, we lack the ability to select the most relevant mechanisms.

The third criticism is the tendency to rely only on two theories, agency theory and institutional theory, mostly in isolation but sometimes together. While strong theories are valuable, using two theories is also a weakness since then only two different eyes are used to see with, and rarely both eyes are used at the same time. The latter means that we rarely see when the theories are identical and when they complement or compete [11]. For sure, there is no value as such in a multitude of theories, since it can create a chaos of understanding. But especially the competition between strong theories is desirable, as it develops each theory and provides a more nuanced understanding.

The present paper does not take on the tremendous task of creating an ecological theory of corporate governance. Instead, to begin the journey toward such a theory, the paper reverts to the traditional view by focusing on one mechanism—the ownership structure—but infuses an ecological perspective, regarding ownership as a system with ecological characteristics of interaction.

The ownership structure

For Adam Smith [18] ownership of the firm was simple. One single person baked bread and sold the bread to customers, not with the motive of ensuring customer survival, but rather for the baker's own livelihood. There was no corporate governance issue since the firm consisted of the baker him/herself. The corporation, i.e., the joint stock company, containing

more than one owner, existed in Smith's time, but according to him it suffered from shareholder and managerial ignorance and disinterest. Only for example banks and channel corporations could be organised as joint stock companies since their operations were relatively simple and difficult to mismanage.

The joint stock company developed during the 19th century and with it emerged mechanisms to influence corporate direction, which presumably made the legal form of the joint stock company survive and flourish, despite Smith's condescending judgment that it was burdened with disinterested shareholders and managers lacking the existential drive of Smith's baker.

The increase in the number of shareholders was observed by many researchers at the start of the 1900s, with the peak reached by Veblen [19], Berle and Means [2] and Burnham [3], who predicted the large number of shareholders created a governance vacuum to be filled by managers. It is a strange conclusion since the shareholders were assumed to be capitalists, with a single common interest, profit. Preference identity among all the shareholders would create the same push for profitability as would one or two shareholders. However, the single shareholders in the dispersed ownership structure had no interest in making sure that the corporation used its resources profitably, since shareholders act only for themselves and are unwilling to expend effort for the benefit of others. This is the shareholding tragedy, a tragedy of the commons, where the single parties have no incentive to interact and to cooperate in order to exploit the resources for the collective benefit of shareholders. So, the owners lost their power, not due to preference differences, but due to weak or absent incentives to influence the corporation. In the system of governance that had developed during the 19th and early 20th century, no mechanism appeared to compensate for this lack of control. This situation implied the governance vacuum created by absent shareholders was filled with management power, which gave Burnham the title of his book '*The Managerial Revolution*'. Although it is an overly dramatic conclusion, managers have indeed significant power and a strong influence over the firm, and today we can also recognize that managers are not only managing the firm but also act as active participants in corporate governance [5].

More recently, owners have regained in power through development in governance mechanisms—for example the fashion of single business strategy, making it easier to evaluate the corporation, and the development of accounting systems such as IFRS, making it easier to understand the economic development of the corporation. Additionally, new shareholders have arrived, especially large financial funds that can either influence the corporation as investors through influencing the stock market and its product, the share price, by selling/buying shares, or they can act as owners, i.e., shareholder activists influencing through the mechanisms of annual meetings of shareholders and/or board composition.

In research, studies have largely adhered to the simple Bearle and Means' [2] idea that ownership capacity and influence are indicated by ownership concentration, assuming owners are identical in preferences and influence capacity, while ignoring social actions created by owners in interaction with each other. One effect of this idea, termed separation of ownership and control, is that studies focus on ownership concentration, disregarding owner identity and the possibility of owner interaction.

More recently, however, studies have recognised the importance of owner diversity [7, 8]. This involves relinquishing the assumption of identical owners differing only in ownership power. Instead, diversity of owners is acknowledged. In its simplest form, this appears in studies of corporations with one owner category, most commonly family firms. More advanced approaches consider ownership structures with multiple owner categories, e.g., family owners, entrepreneurial owners, financial funds. The categorization is based on owner attributes, such as owner preferences, assuming similarity within categories, but can also use other attributes (to be presented later, under 'Owner attributes').

This opens for explanations that specific owner categories influence corporations in specific ways, and that corporations with certain characteristics attract or repel specific owner categories—an ownership client effect. Thus, the owner categories in the ownership structure can be both a cause and an effect of corporate direction.

Even more interesting is research acknowledging ownership structures consisting of several different owners. Then it becomes possible to consider

the mix of owner categories in the ownership structure and how combinations influence the corporation—for example, how ownership category A and ownership category B influence the corporation.

With this development, one further step can be taken: toward the ecology of ownership structure. This means not only considering how owner A and owner B independently influence corporations, but also how their possible interaction influences outcomes—i.e., treating ownership as a system with ecological features.

The step towards an ecological view of ownership structure is yet to be taken. While some studies, often case-based [17], have considered owner interactions, we lack statistical hypothesis testing, partly due to data issues but mainly due to the absence of theories conceptually capturing owner interactions and predicting their influence. However, with the development of the idea of constellations (e.g., an ownership structures or boards) and empirical inductive methods such as fuzzy set qualitative comparative analysis fsQCA [15], it is now possible to analyse factors simultaneously influencing outcomes. Indeed, this represents a step toward abandoning *ceteris paribus*.

The ecological view of ownership structure

Since the ecological view is centred on the system dynamics of the ownership structure, we need to have conceptions of the ownership structure, the owners and their interactions, which constitute the dynamic process of the ownership structure. Then we can continue by using ideas from theories and concepts to relate interactions to outcomes.

Ownership structure characteristics

The ownership structure consists of a set-up of owners organized according to their voting rights. These owners can influence the corporation directly or through interactions with other owners. The processes of multiple interactions between owners can influence the corporation and ultimately the performance of the corporation, but interactions can also influence the set-up of owners through exit and entry of owners, which gives the ownership structure a tendency towards dynamic equilibrium.

Owner attributes

Owners in an ownership structure can be characterized using attributes. Here three attributes were chosen: preferences, governance strategies,

and governance capacities [4]. These attributes can in turn be divided into subcategories:

preferences: risk, control, profit goals, non-profit goals, etc;

governance capacity: voting rights, authority, competence, information, governance costs [4];

governance strategies: company-oriented or financial-oriented [8].

These three attributes of an owner must be considered both for the single owners influence on the corporation, and, more importantly here, for how they influence the interactions between different owners.

Owner types

Owners can be divided into four main categories, the individual entrepreneurs, families, corporations and financial funds (domestic or foreign) [8]. They differ in preferences, for example, individuals have preferences for freedom, families for socio-emotional wealth, corporations for strategic alignment, and funds for profit. The governance strategy of individual entrepreneurs, families, and corporations are company-oriented, while financial funds adopt financial-oriented strategies. Governance capacity is generally strong for individuals, families and corporations, through with different weaknesses due to specific competence restrictions, while funds are characterised by weak governance capacity.

Interaction characteristics

Now it is time to turn to the important part of the ecological view of ownership structure: owner interactions, i.e., when an owner's actions are influenced by and influence other owners. These interactions can be passive or active.

Passive interaction occurs when an owner decides to enter or leave an ownership structure because of the presence or actions of another owner. This resembles the client effect, when entry or exit is due to corporate characteristics or actions. In passive interaction, an owner is attracted or repelled by a belief in synergy effects through the mere presence of other owners, acting separately. Example: a financial fund invests in a corporation dominated by a family owner, believing the combination of a financial fund and a strong family owner will make the corporation stronger by, for example, signalling to the corporation's debt holders that the fund finds the corporation and its strategy credible, thereby maybe lowering the interest

burden of the corporation and by that, increasing the ROA of the corporation. (to be qualified as interaction, it must include an idea of synergy profit or loss, not just investment decisions based on corporate evaluation or stock price).

Active interaction occurs when owners or their representatives come into contact at different arenas and, after interacting, perform actions individually or jointly. Common arenas include the board (or informal gatherings before/after meetings). Interaction ranges from a simple phone call requesting support to lengthy strategy discussions across several board meetings. Interaction entails resource consumption, i.e., costs termed “interaction costs,” which is part of governance costs.

Interaction types

Interactions occur between actors whose attributes will influence the outcome of the interaction. Attribute interaction can be either similar or dissimilar. When the interacting attributes of the owners are more or less similar, they are overlapping. When they are dissimilar, they can either complement each other or they could compete.

Complexity of the ecological view

Now we have a set-up of four different types of owners, characterized by at least three attributes, that can be engaged in passive or active interaction, where the attributes of the owners can either overlap, complement or compete, influencing the corporation and its performance.

Coming to this point, we realize that the ecological view of governance that only observes the ownership structure is a large matrix, consisting of four different types of owners, each with three attributes. In the simplest case, with only two owners, there are three interactions between their preferences, governance strategies and governance capacity. With three owner types we get 9 interactions, with 4 types we get 18 interactions. But that is if we only have one characteristic of the attributes, a simplification bordering on absurdity.

With the ambition of relevance, more characteristics in each attribute will be added, for example, specifying preferences into long-term profit, investment in research, socio-emotional wealth, and so on—which progressively increases the number of interactions. To this we add the multiplication factor of a single interaction that will influence the other

interactions. We understand from this that the matrix of four types of owners with three attributes, each with several characteristics, constitutes many interactions, making it very hard, if not impossible, to deal with all interactions in order to explain corporate performance due to ownership structure.

But the hardship of offering explanations does not stop here. With the ambition of relevance, we add the notion of equifinality [15], the ontological insight that one outcome can be produced in multiple ways. For example, as found by Ponomareva, Strelkova, Collin and Gabaldon [14], the presence of family ownership and domestic and foreign fund ownership in an ownership structure can produce both high and low ROA. Taken out of context, this appears paradoxical, but adding context clarifies: high ROA tends to appear in concentrated ownership structures, while low ROA tends to appear dispersed ones. Probably interactions differ because of the different set-up in attributes taken together, influencing the ROA outcome. The notion of equifinality promotes the ecological view, focusing on the system, noticing the set-up of factors (owners and attributes), the interactions within the system, and how interactions influence other interactions.

Interactions and effects

We can now explore how this conceptual set-up for an ecological view of corporate governance can be used to find interactions and their effects. One common belief, based on demographic studies [12], is that similarities between actors creates an interaction that can improve their joint implementation capacity while differences can improve developmental capacity. It could therefore be claimed that similarity in a specific ownership attribute creates a possibility of synergy in strategy implementation, thus improving corporate performance, especially short-term performance.

Let us use an example of two different corporations.

Corporation A is dominated by a family in its second generation, with a significant but not dominant financial fund owner. The family interacts with the domestic fund, creating high performance through complementary competence (family in industry, fund in finance). However, goal preferences partly compete: fund seeks profitability, family seeks socio-emotional wealth.

Corporation B is dominated by a family in its fifth generation, with

dispersed ownership among many family members, plus a significant fund owner. Preference conflicts are weaker, as family members approach the fund's profitability goals. But competence complementarity is reduced, as later generations lack intimate operational knowledge.

In this example, Corporation A may achieve stronger long-term performance if the difference in goal preferences can be managed, while Corporation B may achieve short-term profit but weaker long-term development due to absence of complementarity. This implies Corporation A likely has a stable ownership structure, while Corporation B may face disinvestment by fund or family, altering ownership composition.

Similarity of attributes can create conservatism, supporting inertia and reducing long-term performance. Dissimilarity, such as goal conflict, can hamper short-term performance but foster long-term development if managed. If owners imagine synergies from complementarities, they have incentives to assume interaction costs to overcome conflicts in attributes. Conversely, similarity may reduce incentives to interact, limiting exploitation of small differences.

In the ecological view, owners possess multiple attributes simultaneously. Some may be similar, others dissimilar. A dissimilarity may be conflictual but also complementary, creating positive synergy if interaction costs are outweighed by expected benefits.

Being more specific concerning attributes, one important aspect of the ownership structure is its power distribution. It comes from the attribute of governance capacity, consisting of voting rights and authority, which can influence incentives to interact.

Power considered as owners voting rights can be symmetrical, i.e., some owners with the highest voting rights have about the same amount of voting rights, or asymmetrical, where one owner have considerably more voting rights than the others.

High symmetry: similarity in governance capacity could be a condition for conflict, like boxers in a ring, especially if preferences differ. However, if owners recognize potential benefits from cooperation, they have incentives to assume interaction costs to manage conflict. Thus, conflict itself does not necessarily reduce performance. It is the net of interaction costs to

manage the conflict and potential interaction benefits that will influence the performance.

High asymmetry: one dominant owner may stabilize governance but reduce incentives for smaller owners to interact.

Take another example, where corporation's ownership structure consisting of an individual and a corporation with symmetrical voting rights. There could be conflict in preference attribute of goals between the individual, that is assumed to have the goal of freedom, and the corporation, that is assumed to have operational synergy goals. In this example, there is one characteristic of an owner attribute, the governance capacity of voting rights, which have similarity, and one characteristic of another owner attribute, preferences of goal orientation, which has dissimilarity that could create conflict. However, while the individual owner typically has governance capacity of intimate knowledge about the firm, maybe both operational knowledge of the firm and intimate knowledge about the firm's markets, the corporation's governance capacity could bring, for example, marketing knowledge and marketing channels. In these characteristics of attributes, the different owners have attributes that are both overlapping and complementary, which can create synergy benefits for the firm if realized through interactions. These interaction possibilities can be utilized through synergy if the owners overcome their goal conflict through assuming the governance costs of interaction costs through negotiating and coordinating.

In sum, we realize that it is hard to make predictions based on theoretical understanding concerning interactions. We can, however, have expectations that conflictual attributes do not reduce performance per se, but can be incentives for interaction when expectation of interaction costs concerning one attribute is less than expected revenues of interactions concerning another attribute.

The dynamics of the ownership structure

With the ecological view comes also the dynamics of ecology, which is the expectation of processes towards equilibrium of the system. Some owners in an ownership structure will exit because they do not experience benefits of interaction—either because they do not find characteristics that

can create benefits through interactions, as in our first example, or because their calculation shows that interaction costs exceed potential benefits.

Potential owners will enter ownership structures if they find benefits of passive or active interaction with some of the present owners. This exit-and-entry tendency makes ownership structures dynamic and unstable. However, since one characteristic of owners' preference attributes is their exit preference—families and entrepreneurs have low probability of exit, while financial funds have high probability—ownership structures can be expected to change in these specific exit-oriented ownership categories. In short, financial funds tend to come and go, while family owners and entrepreneurs persist.

The ecological views demand on empirical studies

The ecological view of ownership structure has theoretical difficulties, as stated above. But it has also some considerable difficulties concerning empirical study of interactions and their effects on the corporation.

Owner interactions can be studied as such, i.e., the very actions produced through owners' interactions. That is, however, hard to do, and is normally only possible in case studies. Even then, it can be difficult to obtain information about actual owner actions and interactions.

An alternative is the black box methodology [13], dominant in governance research, especially board research. Very seldom are the actions performed at actual board meetings studied directly. Instead, researchers "black box" board processes and observe preconditions for action, such as demographic set-up of board members. By using theories about what these characteristics can create, outcomes of board processes are predicted. A similar black box methodology can be used for owner interaction: instead of observing actual actions, researchers study preconditions of actions, such as owners' preferences, governance strategies, and governance capacity, and through relevant theories predict outcomes.

The problem with black box methodology in owner diversity is that we do not know which attributes and their characteristics, or sets of attributes influence interaction between different owners. Thus, the empirical problem directs us back to theory, where we need to develop expectations of which characteristics of attributes influence interactions and how these produce outcomes.

Yet, some studies single out attributes that explain outcomes of owner actions on corporations, for example, preferences, governance strategy orientation, voting power, and governance capacity. But how these attributes influence other owners and their interactions, producing actions that affect the corporation, is still an unexplored theoretical domain. Instead, we are left with more or less clever speculations based on theories judged as relevant.

However, with contributions from inductive studies, especially those using the fuzzy set qualitative comparative analysis (fsQCA), such as [14] and [15], we get empirically induced relationships that can be a base for theoretical development.

Another empirical issue for the ecological view is the dynamics inherent in ecology, which put specific demands on empirical method. Due to potential instability of an ownership structure, a synchronic study observing ownership at one moment cannot differentiate between stable and unstable structures. This forces the ecological view to recommend a longitudinal method.

Conclusion

An ecological view of the ownership structure has been presented, containing four different types of owners characterized by three attributes, engaged in passive or active interaction, where the attributes either overlap, complement or compete, thereby influencing the corporation and its performance. The focus has been on the process of interactions, where one conception “similarity-dissimilarity” often used in demographic studies, has been applied to understand how interactions create effects.

Other conceptions and theories could, and indeed should, be used to develop the ecological view, ultimately making it possible to predict outcomes and test them. In an interaction with Copilot, other theories were suggested. For example, the attribute of governance capacity includes resources, which could make it relevant to apply resource dependency theory and power-oriented theories such as Marxism. Since there are several actors interacting an obvious application would be treat it as a game, thus applying game theory. Interactions could be repeated, thus creating networks, and they could have been built over time, implying the possibility of trust relationships, which together invite network theory applications.

However, a goal of testing predictions, which is Popper's demand on a legitimate theory, may be hard to achieve. The ecological view requires that numerous factors and their interactions be considered simultaneously and longitudinally—without escaping into simplicity via *ceteris paribus*.

Having said that, a disappointing conclusion is very close at hand: the ecological view may be impossible. It seeks ontological closeness to the reality, aiming for high relevance. But a theory approaching reality risks failing on at least two of Popper's quality criteria: parsimony and pragmatism. The ecological view risks becoming very complicated, the opposite of being parsimonious. A parsimonious theory is unlikely to be pragmatic, i.e., easily usable by non-professors of the ecological view.

However! The Boeing 777 would not have existed without those who, in the late 19th century, tried to do what their failed flights showed was impossible: flying. We may never arrive at a good ecological theory of corporate governance. But if we do not try, we will most certainly not reach it.

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